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MANAGING SCHOOLS IN SECURITY CHALLENGED ENVIRONMENT: IMPLICATIONS FOR TEACHERS' PROFESSIONAL PEDAGOGICAL COMMITMENT IN THE 21ST CENTURY

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ABSTRACT

Security challenges hinder teachers' professional-pedagogical, commitment, created by numerous treats to life and properties seen in kidnapping cases, rape, security lapses, uncertainties, lack of job stability, environmental hazards, crowdedness of classrooms, lack of infrastructures and equipment, breakdown of law and order, indiscipline, arm robbery, police brutality, cultism, hostage-taking, disruption of economic, social, political and educational programs and policies. This paper, therefore submits that teachers' commitment closely relates to teachers' pedagogical performance and ability to innovate and integrate new ideas into practices. Teachers spend much time and effort on school achievement, with commitment seriously impeded by the numerous security challenges. Some recommendations were therefore offered like increasing security presence, and installing perimeter walls to discourage free and unsolicited access to the schools, these walls are to be monitored and visitors should be check-in and out of the gates. Visitors are also to be issued distinct identification required to be worn. The perimeter fences should contain barriers, alarm systems, and lighting mostly at night. The environment of the school should be improved upon to discourage truancy and absenteeism and provide a good drainage system, large classrooms, and functional facilities/equipment. Damage roofs, windows, floors, and nonfacilities be immediately put in order.

KEYWORDS

Security challenges, indiscipline, environmental, commitment, pedagogy.

Background to the Study

The world is facing security challenges generally and schools in Nigeria are not left out. Considering the various security experiences, Nigeria cannot be said to be able to maintain environment where people operate equally; where there is peace and secured environment; the economy is vibrant and of course the citizens, especially youths, have hopes.

Writing on security challenges, Enudi (2018), research says most secondary schools in south-south geopolitical zone are faced with security challenges which affect teachers and students Stella Maris Mixed Secondary School Ashaka witnessed kidnapping of a teacher and students in 2015. In 2017 youths are reported to invade St. Pius Catholic Grammar School Onicha-Ugbo holding the principal hostage for several hours in his office. In media channels, one could hear of different security challenges ranging from cultism, kidnapping, bullying and theft, which make teachers and students feel less safe, harder to learn and for teachers to do their jobs effectively

In general, school environment can be described as not safe in Nigeria The abduction of 110 Dapchi and 300 Chibok female students' all in the Northern area of Nigeria leaves schools in the vulnerable window of helplessness as far as security and safety of teachers and students are concern. Fire exists and fire extinguishers are not easily found; fire drill is not a culture, and there is general lack of knowledge about safety among teachers and even the students. If a child's life is compromised or ruined because the school failed to do what is reasonably practicable to guarantee students' safety, the school will find itself wanting legally. Schools weather public or private, risk losing patronage and profitability as security lapses may necessitate parents to withdraw their children from school, and teachers migrate to other environment for job. These have serious impact on teachers pedagogical commitment because security is a priority needs for every human being.

There are issues of missing kids especially during the 'ember' months that is September to December. Stories of ritual killings made the rounds in Niger-Delta region especially Bayelsa, Delta, Edo, Rivers and Cross River States of Nigeria. There was a story of a school child kidnapped in Delta State, using a sack, and tricycle, the boy's cry attracted the driver of the tricycle to ask about the content of the sack. The driver was not satisfied with the kidnapper's answer so drove straight to the union's office where the kidnapper was arrested and beaten to death.

Using Lagos State Nigeria, Yusuf and Idogho (2016), reported that a young boy was beaten up around Cement bus stop area of Lagos State accused of taking a school child to ritual killers for money making process.

From the cited cases, some common description of security challenges include: want of safety, danger, hazard, uncertainty, lost of confidence, doubt. These different descriptors, however, run into a common conference; to a state of vulnerability to harm and loss of life, property or livelihood. However, it can be clearly stated that Nigeria has remained more insecure because of the various ethnic religious and political crises since 2011 after the presidential election. This takes the shape of bomb blasts sponsored by the Boko Harmam religious sect. the unparalleled spate of terrorism, kidnappings and other violence crimes is to say the least, alarming. Religious leaders, churches, mosques and schools are not left out in this onslaught. There is no gainsaying the fact that Nigeria is at a cross-road and gradually drifting towards a failed nation if this insecurity trend continues.

Consequently, in the South-West Nigeria, armed robbers have taken over, while in the North, cross-border bandits operate with ease. However, in the South-South, Nigeria, there are rampant cases of kidnapping and oil bunkering. Also, the incessant ways of crime and armed robbery attacks, all point to the fact that security challenge is fast becoming a norm in Nigeria generally and the Niger-Delta region of Nigeria in particular. The end-products lead to the decimation of innocent lives, disruption of economic activities, and properties, disruption of education calendar, curriculum and non-availability of staff, poor enrolment of students' poor school attendance, and low graduate quality output with consequences of total breakdown of quality of education.

Incidence of police brutality, corruption, violence, murder and abuse of power has punctuated almost every aspect of the society. Armed robbers in Nigeria operate almost freely in the society, using deadly weapons. Even the ordinary man on the street who is expected to be supportive of the police often have serious misgiving when confronted with the alleged massive mutual aids granted to the criminals by some members of the police force.

According to Anho (2014), security challenges can be attributed to several factors such as unemployment, and underemployment of Nigerian graduates from tertiary institutions across the country. Corruption and poverty also constitute serious challenges. So many Nigerians face economic depression, lack of freedom, inability to provide the basic needs of life for self and family, lack of access to loans and credit, facilities and inability to save or own assets.

The incessant bombing by Boko Haram insurgents in the North, kidnapping in the South-West, militancy in South-South no doubt impact negatively on lives, property and educational development of Nigeria. Though, there is dearth of quantitative evaluation of the catastrophic attacks, available statistics has it that between July 25 and February 2011, Human Right Watch (2012) reported a total death toll of 935 persons in 164 attacks. It was also reported that an estimate of 550 people were killed through bombing and other means: 550 persons were killed in 135 attacks in 2011 alone. While in 2011, at least 500 people were killed in Boko Haram attacks (Amnesty International, 2012). This number would have appreciated greatly in 2020. Apart from the loss of lives, there is also wanton destruction of property worth several billions of naira through bombing (Oluwaseun, 2012). The above scenario has dire consequences for school administration, teacher's, pedagogical commitment and sustainable educational development generally.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this study is based on the human relations theory of Mary Parker Follett and school climate theory as propounded by Halphin and Croff (1963), who was a political, business and social philosopher. In the 1920s, Mary Follett initiated the idea of contingency or situation approach in "the law of the situation" in which she explains that different situations require different kinds of knowledge, and the man who possesses the knowledge demanded by certain situations tends, in the best managed businesses all things being equal to become the leader of the moment. Problems can be hand through "coordination" which she considers as key to building an effective organization.

Follett basic contention was that any enduring society or organization must be based upon recognition of the motivating desires of individuals and of group. She believes that all organizational programmes are fundamentally human relations

Coordination was expressed in four fundamental principals of organization according to Peretomode (2013) are: Coordination by direct contact of the people concerned, instead of the classical or traditional notion of hierarchy of autonomy, Coordination in early stages; that direct contact should begin as policy is being formulated by school manager rather than after it has been formed, Coordination as reciprocal relating to all the factors, in a situation taking into account, parts and their interaction in the situation being handled, and Coordination as a continuous phrase. This involves coordination at initial stages of planning, and implementation, coordination in evaluating the progress and coordination in taking the financial decision.

School climate theory as propounded by Halphin and Croft in (1963), states that a sustainable positive school climate fosters youth development and makes learning necessary for a productive, contributory and satisfying life in democratic society.

School climate theory posits that safe and secured school climate has its significant influence on educational outcomes. It posits that positive school encourages interpersonal relationship and optimal learning opportunities for all students and reduce disruptive behaviour which school climate theory refers to as the quality and character of the school life. It is based in patterns of school life experience and reflects norms, goals, values, interpersonal relationship, teaching, learning and leadership practices, and organizational structure.

According to the proponents, the school can be a relatively enduring quality of the internal environment of school experienced by members, which influences behaviour of staff, students and school administrators.

This theory is related to this study because a positive school climate will improve security and safety for staff and students. Positive school climate has been associated with fewer internal wrangling, and behavioural problems and less external and internal attacks, as such the environment becomes Secures and Safe. Therefore, the two theories are relevant to this work because there should be good coordination in all ramification of plans, policies and activities of school to create a situation of safety and secure environment for teaching and learning.

Kidnapping and Hostage Taking as Security Challenge

Kidnapping is a violent, terrible, sensational crime and poses national security challenges for any country. One will rightly say that kidnapping gained momentum in Nigeria as a response to joblessness, moral decadence, hopelessness and frustration among the youths. According to Ordu, (2015), it is results from politicians and disgruntled individuals who seized the opportunity to perpetuate criminality. The miscreants use this criminal model easiest method for intimidating human beings for easy access to cash and properties.

Hostage-taking and kidnapping are intermingled evil, enthralled by criminals, with characteristic features of crime or violence. The crime of hostage taking/kidnapping has grown over the years. It has been adopted as an industry for abducting political rivals, Heads of government institutions, business mogul and financially advantage persons in the society. In schools it extends to vice chancellors/provosts/rectors, deans, heads of departments, lecturers, students' union officials and other students male and female perceived as opponent to political position or erotic love relationships.

Citing related happenings, Odumbo, Shittu, Akinyemi, and Momoh (2017), cited incidences of kidnapping in Lagos state Nigeria which are forcing schools to approach insurance companies and security agencies for protection of students and most government and private school owners are also seeking helps from Police Commands and private security outfits to protect their students and employees from being kidnapped. Explaining further Odumbo et al., (2017), noted that, security agencies are forging stronger ties with their local counterpart on how to beef up security across the six (6) Education District in the state. It is obvious that kidnapping cases was rampant in schools and the target of kidnapper is to collect ransom fee from rich parents. Some schools have to negotiate with some private security enterprise being main targets of kidnappers and most of them do not employ or equip armed guard to protect students. If security guards were equipped with guns and other arm instruments, the attack will reduce to barest minimum if not totally eradicated.

Schools in Lagos metropolis have been targeted by kidnappers with the ultimate objective of making money through payment of ransom. On Thursday, May 25, 2017 it was reported that the notorious gang of gunmen abducted six (6) students from Lagos State Model College, Igbonla-Epe, Lagos. These students include: Yusuf Farouk, Ramon Isiaka, Pelumi Phillips. Peter Jones Adebajo George and Judah Agbaosi, abducted at about 5am, when a section of the school fence was broken down. That was the second time of student abduction in the school. Three suspects were arrested in Benin by the Inspector General of Police's intelligence response team in connection with the students' abduction. The suspects include: Egelu Endurance, 25 years, aka (Jubby): Stanley Yomi Irabomini, 25 years, aka (Powei) and Bentel Endurance, 24 years all from Ovia South Local Government Area of Edo State, Nigeria.

Furthermore, in January 2017, three students, three female supervisors, one female cook and a female Turkish teacher were also reported to be kidnapped at Nigeria Tulip International College, Isheri, Ogun State. The kidnappers demanded N1.2bn for the release of the abducted persons (Punch, 17 June, 2017). Kidnapping and hostage taking atrocity can be said to has been industrialized in Nigeria metropolis which involve: artisan, unemployed youth, gangsters, community hooligans a.k.a. (Badoo), terrorists, ritualists, spiritual father of several religious grows as prime suspects of such atrocities, victims are: vice-chancellors, students, teachers, principals, lecturers, business mogul, politicians and Royal fathers are the major target of kidnappers.

Most of these schools have faced problems of insecurity and safety of teachers and students. In 2015, there was a case of kidnapping of a teacher at Stella Maris Secondary School Ashaka, Delta State. In 2017, youths invaded the St. Pius Catholic Grammar School Onicha Ugbu Delta State holding the school principal hostage for several hours in his office. In media channels one could hear of different insecurity issues ranging from kidnapping, rape, bullying and theft, which make teachers and students less secure within school environment and it makes it harder for students to learn and for teachers to do their jobs effectively.

It was reported on NTA news that on Friday 24th 2012, residents of commercial city Abia (Aba) live in fear following the kidnapping of 15 school children whose school bus was hijacked by kidnapers demanding N20 million ransom before they could be released. Two teenagers were arrested for kidnapping and raping a 16-year-old school girl in Bauchi while four students were arrested for assaulting Lagos school girls in broad daylight, (Punch News 2017).

Rape as Security Challenge

Associate with kidnapping, specifically, Okunola (2008), identified problem associated with school insecurity to include rapping that at the special education centre in Jada in Adamawa state primary school, pupil was raped by the teacher. This makes the child to enter into early pregnancy while at the same time contracting of deadly infections disease.

Such insecurity situations promote fears, loss of lives and property and time limiting students' performance in the schools. For instance, those that passed May/June examination were as follows 20% in 2007, 26% in 2008, and 2009 23% in 2010 and 30% in 2011, (Jimada, 2017). For western education to survive in Nigeria, it is pertinent to consider security issues and problems that have affected and capable of affecting the attitude, commitment and confidence of school personnel. Some of the major security problems currently confronting the nation in general and schools in particular have been identified as follows:

According to Public Safety Opera News (2020), a University of Benin female student Uwaila Omozuwa 22 years old undergraduate was raped and murdered in a church where she was alleged to have gone to read, the Nigerian police is still investigating to identify who the killer is. The Punch News Paper of 9th June, 2020 also reported a case of other students raped at Ibadan by gun men within this period, a University of Jos female student was kidnapped by gun men and demanded for 6 million naira for her release. From these recent happenings, are our Nigerian students actually safe within and outside the school environment.

Environmental Hazards as Security Challenge

A visit to schools shows most have slippery floors, which unsafe environmental conditions that should be dealt with immediately. Hazardous chemicals in school environment can lead to gas poisoning. And highly inflammables substances can start a wild fire. Crowded classrooms, classrooms with single doors, and narrow single exit gates can result in students stepping on each other in during panicky situations. All jeopardizes school safety. In the south-south geopolitical zone of Nigeria, the incessant rains make the school environment water logged, the lawns and classrooms slippery, therefore dangerous to teachers and students.

Looking at Nigerian schools in general, Yusuf and Idoghor (2016), states percentage of schools in Nigeria are not safe. Classrooms are overcrowded, thus obviously call for urgent needs to be infrastructural and environmentally visited for a face look and avoid the catastrophes associated with overcrowded, dilapidated and unsafe environment. If a child's life is compromised or ruined because the school failed to do what is reasonably practicable to guarantee students' safety, the school will be held liable for negligence by parents or guardians. In addition, such schools risk losing patronages as parents could withdraw children because of safety concerns.

Students, parents, teachers, and school administrators have the right to expect their schools to be safe a place of learning. Safety efforts must be focused on improving students' overall sense of environmental, physical, emotional, safety and security.

Writing on environmental problems, Usang (2010), in NAEP conference in Port-Harcourt noted that environment safety consists a threat to the school system. Similarly, on 9th August 2011, principal of Federal College Lejja, Nsukka LG.A of Enugu State, raised alarm over insecurity in school premises. He disclosed this during the college's 13th annual speech and prize giving day ceremony. According to him, "students are in danger over the porosity of the school premises due to absence of perimeter fence with regard to increase in external attack ravaging the country". He further said "school has been cut off from Nsukka town by gullies, created by erosion".

Similarly, Daily Sun (2012), reported how some school children of St. Mary Anglican School, Igbede were drowned when the road to school tipped over. Consequently, according to Anho (2020), erosion is an ecological catastrophe which affects mostly the Niger Delta region of Nigeria, the people constantly feels the ravaging effects of uncontrolled gully erosion, blown off roots of buildings including schools, swampy terrain, overgrown bushes, and bad roads among others. Also, there were cases of numerous displaced villages and schools in the region as school buildings and parents houses were usually affected with its effects on students/pupils enrolment, and attendance. According to Anho (2020), the environmental impact is on the quality of staff who will not want to take appointment or be retained in schools in the Niger Delta region. Specifically, the Niger Delta region has about 75% of its land under water.

Indiscipline as Security Challenge

Factors that contribute to insecurity in schools according to Kirui, Mbugua and Sang (2011), are those mainly associated with indiscipline of students; where students, teachers, subordinate staff and school properties are at risk of being harmed or destroyed. A total of 63% of school heads reported having experienced security problems in schools. In Kindiki (2009) study 70% security guards indicated they have had security challenges in schools they were guarding and nature of security challenges faced by school included strikes, theft of (school or students) property by students, subordinate staff and local community, sneaking, fighting among students, arson and trespassing. All these are indiscipline acts.

The research of Brener, Lowry and Barrios (2015), ranked factors of insecurity by prefects as follows; 63% (stealing), 23.8% (drug abuse), 17.4% (destruction of property), and (5.3%) (assault). This concurred with the head teachers, ranking of 78%, indiscipline as a major cause of insecurity in schools with drug abuse being the major cause (38.1%), followed by peer pressure (33.3%), family factors (14.3%), student's home location (urban/rural) (9.5%) and by overloaded curriculum (4.8%). The above finding is similar to Ngesu, Ndiku and Masses (2008) and by Otieno and Ofulla (2009) which discovered the most commonly abused drugs are alcohol, cigarettes, bhang and Khat (Miraa). Drug abuse is usually associated with aggressive behaviour, irritability and over excitement among other anti-social behaviours; this leads to violence and destruction of property in schools.

Security Challenges and Teachers Professional Pedagogical Commitment

Teachers job commitment includes having knowledge, skills, attitudes, recognition and strategic thinking, which presupposes conscious and intentional decision making involving teachers pedagogy with high acceptance and involvement. These factors contribute to the quality of teaching, which are judged as the professional competence of the teacher, these includes subject knowledge, matter, pedagogical content, knowledge of teaching and learning, curriculum knowledge, teaching experience, and certification status.

Teacher's commitment reflects the degree of internal motivation, enthusiasm; job satisfaction, efficacy and effectiveness. The improvements in the commitment of teachers are one of the outcomes that is likely to be positively affected by the new teacher reform efforts. Researchers argued for increasing commitment of teachers an important step in the process of pedagogical reform. Hence, Becker (2012), defined commitment as investment in particular career, in this case. In a related manner Lortic (2015), commitment is willingness an individual enacts in investing personal resources to the teaching task. Commitment is important for teachers because it reflects a personal interpretation of work experience as absorbing and meaningful.

Professional commitment is typically conceptualized as a positive, affective attachment to one's work. Professional commitment is feeling of dedication among individuals of a group towards their profession. The strength of any profession depends upon the degree of commitment of its members. Teaching is no exception, this means that strength of teaching profession depends upon the commitment of teachers.

Commitment is an essential element of successful teaching. Committed teachers are concerned with the development of students and they profoundly struggle on how to keep students learning effective. They cultivate students' curiosity and interest in learning. Commitment to students learning can be an important factor in motivating students. Committed teachers recognize and endeavour to fulfill responsibilities to students. The degree of loyalty committed teachers have, towards their profession is distinguished characters. Teachers engaged in their profession and committed, play crucial role students in development (Rowe, 2012). Commitment to teaching contributes to teachers' behaviour, attitudes, perceptions and performances (Thapan, 2016). Committed teachers have a tendency to perform the roles effectively their job requires and establish good teacher-student relationship in accordance with professional values.

Teachers' commitment to institution in education manifests itself in identifying with school, feeling like a part of the school, and being loyal to the school. The desire of teachers spending more time in the class and at school, making more effort for school achievement are among contributing causes of commitment to school.

Conclusion

Security challenges hinder teachers' professional pedagogical, commitment, this is as a result of fear created by the numerous treats to life and properties seen in kidnapping cases, rape, security lapses, uncertainties, lack of job stability, environmental hazards, over-crowdedness of classrooms, lack of infrastructures and equipments, breakdown of law and order, as a result of indiscipline, arm robbery, police brutality, cultism, hostage taking, disruption of the economic, social, political and educational programmes and policies.

This paper, therefore submit teachers commitment which is closely related to teachers' pedagogical performance and their ability to innovate and to integrate new ideas into their own practice, manifests itself in identifying with the school, feeling like a part of the school, and being loyal to the school. The desire of teachers spending more time in the classroom and at school, making more effort, for school achievement, and approving compatibility of administration are among contributing causes of commitment to school which is seriously impeded by the numerous security challenges and when a teacher is not committed, the primary aim of education will be defeated. The pedagogical profession skills of such teachers ought to have put in are hindered.

Management Implication

Management involves planning, coordination, supervision, control, motivation and evaluation among others task. Coordination and motivation is pivotal to commitment of workers. Using Mary Parker Follett administrative principles and school climate theory as propounded by Halpin and Croff (1963), that any enduring society or organization must be based upon recognition of the motivating desires of individuals and of groups. While Follett believes that all organizational programmes are fundamentally human relations, Coordination as reciprocal relating to all the factors, in a situation taking into account, parts and their interaction in the situation being handled, and Coordination as a continuous phrase. This involves coordination at initial stages of planning, and implementation, coordination in evaluating the progress and coordination in taking the financial decision as it affect the school security and environment. Teachers will be committed to their professional pedagogy if their needs as it relates to security are well planned, coordinated, supervised and evaluated regularly.

Recommendation

The following recommendations are made to ameliorate or totally eradicate the security challenges so as to have teachers' professional pedagogical commitment;

1. There should be increase security presence in and around every school environment. These can be done by liaising with public law enforcement and private security agencies.
2. Installing perimeter fence/walls around every school to discourage free and unsolicited access to schools. The perimeter fences/walls should be monitored and visitors should be check in and out of the gate. According to Begar (2012), visitors are to be issued distinct identification they are required to wear while on school. The perimeter fences should contain barriers at the top, lightening mostly at night, and alarms system
3. The environment of the school should be improved upon to discourage truancy and absenteeism. Provide good drainage system, large class rooms and functional facilities/equipment. Damage roofs, windows, floors and other facilities should be immediately put in order.
4. Security devices/gadgets should be installed in strategic places. This should include the use of sounds/alarms system or signals, others include metal detector, batons, spray, two ways radio, and touché light among others.
5. To enhance school security and safety, parents, students, teachers, school administrators and all stake holders should be afforded security education so as to understand their roles in the safety and climate of the school.
6. To improve school climate, security and safety, religious, ethnics, gender, political and social differences should be discouraged among all stakeholders in the school business.

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